

Project Charter

PROJECT OVERVIEW

PROJECT NAME

Bringing HTR to the HPC: A Pilot to Customize eScriptorium for Princeton part of the Princeton Open HTR Initiative: Creating Infrastructure for Modeling Historical Texts

PRIMARY INVESTIGATOR

Marina Rustow
Helmut Reimitz
Christine Roughan

GRANT

CDH Research Partnership

EXPECTED START DATE

2024-07-17

EXPECTED END DATE

2025-05-30

DATE OF DOCUMENT

2024-07-12

PROJECT DETAILS

PROJECT ABSTRACT

The Princeton Open HTR Initiative is a research infrastructure project to test a Princeton-specific instance of the eScriptorium handwritten text recognition (HTR) software.

While the digitization efforts of recent decades have revolutionized access to historical texts in libraries, archives and cultural heritage institutions, HTR is making these digitized materials machine readable, opening them up to text search and computational analysis at scale. An increasing number of humanities scholars – including at Princeton – are eager to integrate HTR into their research workflows. But barriers to entry can be significant, particularly in technical expertise and cost.

In this research partnership with the CDH, we will set up and evaluate a test instance of eScriptorium, the current leader in open-source HTR software designed by and for scholars working with historical texts. Our aim is to assess, evaluate and document what it would take to set up and maintain an infrastructure for Princeton researchers, regardless of technical background, corpus size, language, or team size to use freely, efficiently, effectively and sustainably. This phase, exploring modifications to the eScriptorium software to function in a HPC environment like Princeton's Research Computing, is a critical first step towards realizing that goal.

PURPOSE/AUDIENCE

1. Princeton researchers who will be beta testers
2. Research Computing and PUL, who will consider implementing a

	<p>longer-term version of the instance</p> <p>3. HTR community, who will benefit from the enhancements to the eScriptorium code and learn from the Princeton model of implementing an institutional instance</p>
<p>DELIVERABLES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation and code for working with eScriptorium in Princeton HPC environments Code ▾ Must-Have ▾ Internal report assessing further code developments to eScriptorium, Kraken, or related libraries that improve HTR workflows (e.g., better permissions for team projects; better handling of duplicate model files; use of ATR engines besides Kraken) Writing (articl... ▾ Should-Have ▾ Internal report finalizing specs and requirements for long-term management of an HTR infrastructure at Princeton Writing (articl... ▾ Must-Have ▾ White paper published on Zenodo on findings and recommendations for other institutions/projects Writing (articl... ▾ Must-Have ▾ Internal presentation to Princeton stakeholders (RC, PUL, SC) Presentation (... ▾ Must-Have ▾
<p>OUT OF SCOPE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued support by the CDH for the test eScriptorium instance after the test phase or for any of the data or models used or generated during the test phase Production of HTR and segmentation models Production of transcriptions using the eScriptorium software Development of code for additional enhancements to eScriptorium beyond adaption for HPC environments
<p>SUCCESS CRITERIA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Code contributions successfully allow deployment of eScriptorium in Princeton's HPC environment
<p>SUSTAINABILITY PLAN</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The test instance will be shut down after the Research Partnership ends. The code will be available on GitHub so that Princeton or other institutions can fork it and use it.

MILESTONES

Key Milestones	Est. Start Date	Est. End Date
Pre-partnership meetings with collaborators (PUL, RC, UPenn, U Maryland, members of eScriptorium team)	2024-01-08	2024-05-31
Project kickoff	2024-07-17	2024-07-17
Assessments of eScriptorium deployment options (e.g. manual installation, docker, Ansible) and the "slurmer" library complete	2024-07-22	2024-07-26
Test instance of base eScriptorium using the chosen approach deployed	2024-08-12	2024-08-21
Code adaptations produced for integration with HPC	2024-08-19	2025-01-22
Meeting with PUL & RC to determine organizational constraints and requirements	2024-09-06	2024-09-06
Beta testers secured	2024-08-12	2025-01-31
eScriptorium test instance ready for beta testing on library VM (cloud or local)	2024-09-09	2025-01-22
Beta users training and kickoff	2025-01-31	2025-02-07
Mid-term feedback acquired from beta testers	2025-03-07	2025-03-21
End-term feedback acquired from beta testers	2025-04-22	2025-05-06
Internal report(s), white paper, and presentation written	2025-05-07	2025-05-30
Project closeout	2025-05-07	2025-05-30

DEPENDENCIES & RISKS

DEPENDENCIES

- HPC access
- Potential TigerData integration
- Potential external software library (slurmer)
- PUL VMs

POTENTIAL RISKS

- The software might ultimately not work with existing Princeton infrastructure.
- The test instance might not be taken up for longer-term support.
- Beta users will need to be clear that this is a testing phase of the software; they will be advised to download any data they care about before the test instance is shut down.

RIGHTS + PERMISSIONS

- eScriptorium code is open-source and licensed under The MIT License.

PROJECT TEAM

Name	Role on Project	Dept	Role Description
Marina Rustow	Project Co-Lead	NES ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in planning discussions • Test and review the Scriptorium instance
Helmut Reimitz	Project Co-Lead	HIS ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in planning discussions • Test and review the Scriptorium instance
Christine Roug...	Project Co-Lead Project Manager	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate planning meetings and community engagement • Provide feedback on the technical development • Co-author (with the RSE) the internal report(s) and white paper
Rebecca Koeser	RSE	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attend planning meetings as needed • Review and test eScriptorium code and related tooling (potentially including, python API library for eScriptorium, Kraken OCR library, Slurmer) • Coordinate installation of a test instance of eScriptorium • Identify significant points where software engineering could improve an HTR pipeline built around eScriptorium and Kraken • Identify the changes needed to deploy a long-term, supportable instance of eScriptorium at Princeton • Co-author (with Christine) the internal report(s) and white paper
Mary Naydan	Technical Project Manager	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help define, queue, and prioritize work for RSE • Advise Project Manager

Jeri Wieringa	Project Advisor	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advise on the project
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BUDGET

Item	Funding Source	Cost
[budget available upon request]	████████████████████	████████████████████

TERMS OF COLLABORATION

DOCUMENTATION + COMMUNICATION	<p>This research partnership will store its meeting notes and documentation in a shared folder within the CDH Research Partnership shared Google Drive. Asana will be used for task assignment and a Slack channel will be created for technical communications between the project RSE and project manager. The project manager will circulate high level overviews (progress updates and meeting summaries) to all members of the team via regular email. A private Github repository under the Princeton-CDH organization will be used for managing technical issues, documentation, and code.</p> <p>There are a variety of meetings expected / planned over the course of this project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> biweekly internal team meetings conversations with Princeton units that provide necessary or relevant infrastructure or services (Research Computing, PUL) meetings with peer institutions that have established local instances of eScriptorium discussions with the eScriptorium team
CREDIT + ATTRIBUTION	<p>Rebecca will be credited for any code or documentation contributed to eScriptorium or other associated projects. All contributors will be credited as authors on the written outputs (preliminary/anticipated authorship: Christine, Rebecca as co-authors for internal report(s); Christine, Rebecca, Helmut and Marina as co-authors for the white paper).</p>
PUBLICITY	<p>The CDH Communications Manager may publicize the project and related information on the CDH website and newsletter, in annual reports, and on select social media (Bluesky, Instagram). The Communications Manager may also work with Princeton’s Office of Communications to publicize the project on Princeton’s main website or in its magazines.</p>

EXTENSIONS	The PI and RSE may request an extension beyond the allotted partnership timeframe by submitting a written rationale to the CDH PM and the CDH AD. Extensions may also be proposed and automatically granted by the CDH PM and CDH AD due to unforeseen delays in the CDH development schedule.
AMENDMENTS	Amendments to the charter should be requested in writing to the project team members, the CDH PM, and the CDH AD. Changes will be recorded in the "Version History" section below. Please also update the date in the charter header.

SIGNATORIES

PREPARED BY	Mary Naydan Christine Roughan	2024-05-24	Original draft here.
REVIEWED BY	Jeri Wieringa	2024-06-22	
REVIEWED BY	Rebecca Koeser	2024-07-03	
APPROVED BY	Jeri Wieringa Natalia Ermolaev Rebecca Koeser Christine Roughan Mary Naydan	2024-07-17	
APPROVED BY PI	Helmut Reimitz	2024-07-22	
APPROVED BY CDH FACULTY DIRECTOR	Meredith Martin	2024-07-24	

VERSION HISTORY

UPDATED BY	Mary Naydan Christine Roughan	2024-07-12	Put original draft into new charter template & revised to incorporate JW & RSK suggestions.
UPDATED BY	Christine M. Roughan	2024-08-12	Adding line for RSE salary to budget, already accounted for by PLI seed grant.

UPDATED BY	Christine Roughan Mary Naydan	2024-12-02	Adjusted RP end date and milestone dates to reflect extensions granted here: Re Extension for HTR2HP...
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Recommended Citation

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